

Lightlike Pseudo-Riemannian Adaptive Gradient Method

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Abstract

We consider the problem of minimizing a function in a pseudo-Riemannian space. We show that under a lightlike constraint, the steepest descent produces an adaptive gradient method.

Notations The Euclidean norm of any vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^m$ ($m \geq 1$) is denoted $\|x\|$. Given a symmetric positive definite matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$, we define the weighted norm $\|\cdot\|_W$ as

$$\|x\|_W = \sqrt{x^T W x}. \quad (1)$$

1 Introduction

The purpose of this paper is to show that a certain pseudo-Riemannian minimization problem leads to an adaptive gradient method. Let us first briefly recall a few related notions of Riemannian optimization (Bonnabel [2013], Zhang and Sra [2016]) and of adaptivity.

Riemannian optimization. In a Riemannian space (\mathbb{R}^m, A) with A a positive definite metric tensor, it was shown by Amari [1998] that the steepest descent direction of some function $f(x)$ is given by the negative natural gradient $-A(x)^{-1} \nabla f(x)$, which is also known as Riemannian gradient descent in more general Riemannian manifolds (see e.g. Boumal [2023]). In the Euclidean scenario $A \equiv I_m$, it boils down to gradient descent.

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Adaptive gradient methods. The idea of adaptivity in gradient-based optimization of a vector parameter x is to use, at every iteration t , a separate learning rate $\lambda_{t,i}$ for each coordinate x_i . In popular approaches such as AdaGrad (Duchi et al. [2011]) and RMSprop (Tieleman [2012]), this is generally achieved by setting $\lambda_{t,i} = \lambda/\sqrt{G_{t,i}}$ where $G_{t,i}$ is a scalar summary of the history of squared i -th partial derivatives up to time t .

As in Bécigneul and Ganea [2018], this work proposes to combine both topics under a block-diagonal metric assumption.

2 Steepest lightlike descent

Pseudo-Riemannian setting. We consider the problem of minimizing a differentiable real-valued function f defined over the pseudo-Riemannian space \mathbb{R}^{m+n} (with $m, n \geq 1$) equipped with the block-diagonal metric tensor given by

$$M(z) = \begin{pmatrix} A(z) & 0_{m \times n} \\ 0_{n \times m} & -B(z) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where for all $z = (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^n$, both $A(z)$ and $B(z)$ are symmetric positive definite matrices. Clearly, M has the metric signature $(m, n, 0)$.

Example 1 (Spacetime). Flat Minkowski spacetime; Lorentzian geometry (see O’neill [1983], Bär [2004]).

Example 2 (Euclidean-Information). See Achab [2024] for an example of an optimization problem under the product metric composed of the Euclidean and Fisher-Rao metrics (Rao [2009]).

Radiant descent. Let us start by introducing a vector we call the “radiant”, which will play in our pseudo-Riemannian framework the same role that the standard gradient plays in Euclidean steepest descent.

Assumption 1 (Regular point). A point $z = (x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^m \times \mathbb{R}^n$ is said regular if

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(z) = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial x_i}(z) \right)_{1 \leq i \leq m} \neq 0_m \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(z) = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial y_j}(z) \right)_{1 \leq j \leq n} \neq 0_n.$$

Definition 1 (Radiant vector). Under Assumption 1, we define the radiant of f at z as:

$$\mathfrak{X}f(z) = \begin{pmatrix} \left\| \frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(z) \right\|_{A(z)^{-1}}^{-1} A(z)^{-1} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(z) \\ \left\| \frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(z) \right\|_{B(z)^{-1}}^{-1} B(z)^{-1} \frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(z) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{m+n}.$$

By analogy with Minkowski spacetime, we say that a vector $v \in \mathbb{R}^{m+n}$ is lightlike¹ at z if

$$\boxed{v^T M(z) v = 0}. \quad (\text{Lightlike})$$

¹Recall that in Minkowski spacetime, a 4D vector $v = (x, y, z, ct)$ is said null or lightlike if $v^T \text{Diag}(1, 1, 1, -1)v = x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - c^2 t^2 = 0$.

Proposition 2. The radiant vector $\mathbf{X}f(z)$ is lightlike at z .

Proof. It holds:

$$\mathbf{X}f(z)^\top \mathbf{M}(z) \mathbf{X}f(z) = \frac{\|\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(z)\|_{\mathbf{A}(z)^{-1}}^2}{\|\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(z)\|_{\mathbf{A}(z)^{-1}}^2} - \frac{\|\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(z)\|_{\mathbf{B}(z)^{-1}}^2}{\|\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(z)\|_{\mathbf{B}(z)^{-1}}^2} = 0.$$

□

We are now ready to state our main result.

Theorem 3. Under Assumption 1, the steepest Lightlike descent direction of f at z is given by the negative radiant vector $-\mathbf{X}f(z)$.

Proof. Let us follow the derivation of the natural gradient from Amari [1998]. Given $z = (x, y)$ and infinitesimal $\epsilon > 0$, we search for $v = (a, b)$ that minimizes $f(z + \epsilon v) \approx f(z) + \epsilon \nabla f(z)^\top v$ under the constraints:

$$\begin{cases} a^\top \mathbf{A}(z) a = 1 \\ b^\top \mathbf{B}(z) b = 1 \end{cases}, \quad (3)$$

ensuring that v satisfies the Lightlike condition

$$v^\top \mathbf{M}(z) v = 0.$$

By the Lagrangian method, we have

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \{\epsilon \nabla f(z)^\top v + \mu_1 a^\top \mathbf{A}(z) a\} = \mathbf{0}_m \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial b} \{\epsilon \nabla f(z)^\top v + \mu_2 b^\top \mathbf{B}(z) b\} = \mathbf{0}_n \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} a = -\frac{\epsilon}{2\mu_1} \mathbf{A}(z)^{-1} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(z) \\ b = -\frac{\epsilon}{2\mu_2} \mathbf{B}(z)^{-1} \frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(z) \end{cases}. \quad (4)$$

Finally, we deduce by combining Eqs. 3-4 that

$$\frac{\epsilon^2 \|\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}(z)\|_{\mathbf{A}(z)^{-1}}^2}{4\mu_1^2} = \frac{\epsilon^2 \|\frac{\partial f}{\partial y}(z)\|_{\mathbf{B}(z)^{-1}}^2}{4\mu_2^2} = 1, \quad (5)$$

which concludes the proof since

$$v = -\mathbf{X}f(z).$$

□

Theorem 3 motivates the following iterative pseudo-Riemannian minimization algorithm.

Definition 4 (Radiant Descent). For step-size $\lambda > 0$, time step $t \in \mathbb{N}$, we define the radiant descent iteration as

$$\boxed{z_{t+1} = z_t - \lambda \mathbf{X}f(z_t)}. \quad (\text{RD})$$

The radiant descent (RD) algorithm borrows ideas from Riemannian optimization, by computing the Riemannian gradient in each of the two groups of coordinates x and y , and from the concept of adaptivity by rescaling the effective learning rates for x and y in terms of the weighted norms of the partial derivatives of the objective function f .

Remark 1 (Adaptive Stochastic RD). A natural way to turn RD into a stochastic algorithm is to replace the squared weighted norms of the full batch gradients with some adaptive moving averages, akin to RMSprop.

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